

SOCIAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF SELF-CONFIDENCE DEVELOPMENT IN FUTURE EDUCATORS

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Abstract. *This article presents scientific and theoretical information on the goals, relationships, transformations, changes in states, and processes of reconstruction of individuals in the development of self-confidence among future educators.*

Keywords: *educator, self-confidence, frontal lobe, self-regulation, self-defense, self-awareness.*

Self-confidence of future educators is a crucial factor that determines the quality of the educational process and enhances teaching effectiveness. Self-confidence in future educators depends on their accurate understanding of their own abilities and potential, stress management skills, social support, and mentoring assistance.

The development of self-confidence in contemporary global psychology is accompanied by a wealth of accumulated materials, which in turn provide scientific and theoretical information about goals, relationships, changes in states, and personality reconstruction. Modern psychology studies, shapes, improves, and develops an individual's mental state, and also ensures the dynamics of transitioning to a new quality level and new conditions, making it an important practical and applied field.

Neurophysiological processes responsible for the development of self-confidence are located in various areas of the brain, with the frontal lobe being particularly important for self-regulation. Damage to the frontal lobe or its congenital pathologies can lead to disruptions in self-control; aggressive and criminal behavior is also often associated with frontal lobe pathologies. Eastern philosophers attached particular importance to the role of self-confidence in personal development and maturity. In particular, Abu Ali ibn Sina paid great attention to the role of the individual in social life. External world and interactions with people influence the development of both positive and negative traits in a person, and thus, the social environment plays a key role in self-control [1]. According to the views of Abu Nasr al-Farabi, the connection between a person and the surrounding world, as well as the role of interpersonal relationships in personal development, were thoroughly examined. The fulfillment of various needs leads a person to the peak of development, which further contributes to the formation of self-confidence. His works also highlight the psychological characteristics of personality and the role of socialization.

It is known that in Kaykavus's work "Qabusnama," the exceptional role of morality and upbringing in human perfection is emphasized. Kaykavus's views address the issue of developing self-confidence as one of the pressing problems. His ideas on adhering to moral norms, truthfulness, humanity, generosity, modesty, and kindness are considered significant. From this, it is evident that Kaykavus interpreted the development of self-confidence as one of the moral qualities indicative of human perfection. Kaykavus's unique contribution lies in the fact that, while preparing the youth for life, he expressed theoretical issues of comprehensive development and applied them in practice, which has retained its value in all eras and under any regime, becoming a guide for life. The development of self-confidence is analyzed in a scientific-theoretical context

in the works of Eastern thinkers. By analyzing the works of these scholars, students gain the opportunity to develop self-awareness. For this reason, there are key indicators that determine the volitional and psychological states of a person. This reflects the image of the surrounding environment. The movement of the body and its adaptation to this environment, the satisfaction of the need to interact with it, signify the establishment of relationships according to the principle of direct or reverse interaction. The process of controlling the correctness of this interaction is of great importance. In the development of self-confidence, social practice plays an important role. Through feedback, actions are compared with their outcomes. The comparison of these outcomes precedes the current state. This demonstrates the possibility of modeling reality. All human volitional actions are directly manifested in the process of communication. This is because stimulating factors that drive actions within their scope ensure the execution of a behavioral program, include the process of searching and selecting options, and reflect a constantly striving volitional activity. The study of the content and function of developing self-confidence is one of the most pressing issues in the psychology of will. The connection between the development of self-confidence with education and upbringing, as well as the targeted and systematic study of this phenomenon in the production and sports sectors, began in the 1950s-60s. However, this does not mean that the phenomenon of developing self-confidence remained outside the attention of psychologists for a long time. In early psychological research, we can observe that certain aspects of developing self-confidence, important for human mental life, were studied. In the literature analysis conducted by N. V. Samoukina, the history of studying the phenomenon of developing self-confidence is discussed in detail [2].

Self-confidence is how a person evaluates their abilities and potential. A. Bandura, in his work, explored the influence of self-esteem on personal achievements. Bandura emphasizes that a person's confidence in their abilities develops through experiences of success and social support. Additionally, self-confidence is a psychological process in which a person perceives their potential and determines their own worth. In his "Theory of Self-Efficacy," A. Bandura examined the impact of self-esteem on personal achievements. He argues that self-confidence contributes to the development of confidence in one's abilities. Personal successes and experiences directly influence the level of self-confidence. One of the scholars who studied the issue of developing confidence from a psychological perspective was Z. Freud. He lists a number of internal psychological agents related to decision-making and behavioral control to explain a person's ability to manage their behavior. Z. Freud analyzes the development of confidence as an instinct of self-defense of the "I." According to him, the development of the "I" automatically leads to an increase in self-confidence. There are several definitions aimed at revealing the essence and content of the concept of developing self-confidence. In particular, in the Great Russian Encyclopedia, the development of self-confidence is interpreted as the conscious control and management of a person's behavior, thoughts, and emotions, as well as the planning of one's own activities[3]. The development of self-confidence allows for the conscious alteration of thoughts and the prevention of negative actions. From the provided definition, it can be concluded that in the process of developing self-confidence, special attention is paid to awareness, self-management ability, and the function of planning. It is also recognized that self-confidence manifests in a person's behavior, views, emotions, and activities. E. B. Sagarelli was one of the first to investigate the issue of developing self-confidence in the sports field and attempted to create a theory of controlling psychological processes. The researcher identifies four phases of these control processes:

1. Informative — motivating.
2. Preliminary — constructive.
3. Central — rejecting.
4. Final — restructuring.

According to E.B. Sagarelli, the relationship between mental activity and its adequacy pertains to the actions that control the personality. Thus, the first phase is the initial stage of developing self-confidence. The initial creative phase of behavior control is reflected and manifested in the correlation with the current state. The third phase — the central and rejecting phase — completes the objective statement, as well as confirms the interrelation of the controlled actions or reveals the existence of a difference between the reflected situation and real practice, or the lack of adequacy between them. In the final phase, work is done to correct and rectify the "incorrectly reflected" reality.

In E.B. Sagarelli's view, the control of any behavior does not always end with correction. At the same time, "it is necessary to consider controlling processes as mental processes that deny them, since it is through these processes that the individual nullifies the influence of inadequate actions in their mental activity." On the other hand, "... control is the final part of a person's mental activity, always participating in the denial, cancellation, and correction of thought processes that do not correspond to objective reality." From the thoughts presented, it can be noted that E.B. Sagarelli revealed the essence of the imperative function of developing self-confidence. In particular, by dividing the development of self-confidence into phases, he attempted to substantiate their content and implementation mechanisms. He also succeeded in revealing the peculiarities of developing self-confidence in actions and mental processes[4].

Self-awareness is the level of understanding by an individual of their abilities, limitations, and possibilities. C. Rogers, in his theory of "Self-Awareness," discusses how an individual defines their thoughts about themselves and how this understanding shapes their confidence. According to Rogers, through self-awareness and adequate self-assessment, an individual strengthens their confidence. Self-awareness is closely related to self-assessment. G. Herbert Mead, in his work, explains how self-awareness is formed through social interactions. According to Mead's theory, the process of self-awareness develops through interaction with society. The level of self-awareness of future educators plays an important role in their professional development. E. Shcherbatykh analyzes the connection between self-awareness and the development of professional skills among future educators. Shcherbatykh shows how the level of self-awareness of future educators affects the effectiveness of teaching [5]. Self-awareness plays an important role in developing self-confidence. From a psychological and pedagogical perspective, the formation and development of self-awareness directly influence the effectiveness of teaching future educators. Special strategies, reflection, and mentoring programs can be utilized for the development of self-awareness. These theories and practical recommendations will help future educators increase their confidence and improve their professional development. R. Kholikov analyzes the role of self-assessment in developing self-confidence. Kholikov demonstrates how confidence can be enhanced by developing the self-assessment skills of future educators [6]. Mentoring and support play an important role in developing self-confidence among future educators. D. Akhmedova studied the role and effectiveness of mentoring in developing self-confidence among future educators. Akhmedova suggests ways to improve the confidence and professional development of future educators through mentoring programs [7].

In our opinion, the development of self-confidence among future educators has significant social-psychological importance. Factors such as stress, social environment, self-assessment, and mentoring influence the self-confidence of future educators.

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